

**INNOVATIVE APPROACH METHODS IN PROVIDING ENVIRONMENTAL
EDUCATION TO STUDENTS BY PRESERVING AND HONORING NATURE**

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Abstract. *This article talks about the use of innovative methods in environmental education by preserving and honoring nature to the reader-youth, it shows about the impact of changes in nature on it by people, as well as the current activity of innovative methods in environmental education by honoring nature that is in society.*

Keywords: *nature, innovation, environment, reader-youth, environmental education, conservation of nature, its correct use, consciousness of the younger generation, protection of natural areas, ecological culture, integration, environmental education.*

Today, the fundamental essence of educational processes in the world is to achieve educational efficiency by teaching students to live and study, Live, give them environmental education, as well as to introduce a paradigm of quality management. In the introduction **to the article**, on global problems in the preservation and proper use of nature, it is worth considering the requirements of the UN fund for child assistance (UNICEF), the European Organization for security and cooperation (OBSE) to improve the technologies of environmental education for students through the protection of natural areas, to form their positive attitude to nature.

In world practice, research work is being carried out by leading scientific centers, higher educational institutions dedicated to the problems of intensive application of modifications of environmental education technologies to the educational process. At the same time, as a universal value, the preservation of nature, the rational use of Natural Resources, the strengthening of the procedure for using environmentally friendly products in the protection of Public Health, and the improvement of mobile and affective models of the absorption of ecological culture into the minds of the younger generation are of paramount importance. This necessitates the continuous education system to teach students the preservation of nature in an integral way, optimize the forms of environmental education, improve their technologies, systematize the criteria of ecological culture, effectively use the variative and integrative approaches to teaching.

As a socio-economic issue in our country, the tasks of implementing targeted and targeted measures to improve the quality of environmental education through the protection of natural areas, to improve the quality of quality indicators in strengthening the health of the population based on the widespread promotion of ecological culture among the population and ensuring a solid integration of Science, Education and. These tasks require optimization of the content of environmental education for students in secondary schools on the basis of interdisciplinary integration, improvement of variative educational programs in the section of classes, effective organization of innovative activities of teachers.

President Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan Sh. M. Mirziyoyev did not say without reason that" it is necessary to improve and further develop the personnel training system, taking into account the changing socio-economic conditions based on the implementation of the reforms established both in the field of education and education and the analysis and generalization of the

experience gained in subsequent years." The above-mentioned requirements for the modernization of the national state system necessitate a revision of all areas of science, including the system of environmental education.

Based on this, focusing on the theoretical aspects of the article, we cannot say that the National Environmental Education and education system fully meets the requirements of this day. Environmental education, promotion and education, as well as environmental education through the protection of natural areas are urgent problems of society.

The state committee for Ecology and Environmental Protection of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Committee for Ecology and Environmental Protection of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the central apparatus of the Departments of Ecology and Environmental Protection of the regions and the city of Tashkent have established special inspections for the formation of waste, their collection, storage, transportation, disposal, processing, burial and realization;

Today we are witnessing the consequences of humanity's negative attitude towards nature. If floods and earthquakes occur in one part of the world, forest fires are observed in another place. Global problems like this had begun to escalate in the second half of the last century as a result of the use of natural resources without taking into account environmental factors. It should be noted that over the long years, the impact on nature has undermined (caused) the natural balance. To date, however, the civilization of mankind, its tomorrow's fate, requires the solution of just such issues. At the moment, efforts to introduce economical, environmentally friendly technologies in solving environmental problems, to consistently carry out conservation measures or to improve industry legislation are not enough to solve them.

Localities ecological culture yuksaltarish, ecological educator bulgan munsabatni time talablarig, nature illiteracy Kelgus klodlar, as asrabaa-avilashina formastanturish anthropogen influence of the Altai territory omillardandir. Bunda environmental education-education is of paramount importance. Because environmental education-the education of nature and the formation of organs that ensure natural restoration, is important. A criminal case has been initiated on this fact, an investigation is underway. Of course, the EU clan Dilida Nudga relatively respected feelings of formationrepresentation and development is important to the notorious document.

Bu, on duty, teacher kadrlar tsimmasiga katta responsibility yuklaidi. Dehkan yillarida mamlatimizda barcha jabhalar a number of ecology and nature experts reasonably adhered to long-term legal legislation-the regulatory framework of yaratildi. Jumladan, Republic of Uzbekistan constitutionality, "the nature of the kallish zilrisida governorate“ gi,”education of the longicide“ gi zakonlar, shuningdek, Bashkir number of environmentalists education-upbringing of the tizimining law is fundamental to the formation of this.

Today's system of life is not the same,the attitude towards nature is also not the same among humans.Paying attention to the practical side of the article, the nature of the alternation of day and night in different geographical zoias is also not the same. The difference between day and night is not felt around the equator. But in zones with an average (temperate) and cold climate, in the summer season the day is long, the night is short, and in winter it is vice versa. This in turn led to the fact that orgagshzmlariing adapted to a long and short day (photopsriode). From the plants of the North, wheat, rye, spinach, cebarga, mingyapraq, sachratqn, gulsapsar, marjumak

(grechikha), qashqargul, millet, sunflower, sage, tobacco, flax and others develop normally on a short day. Light animals play a role in life.

Chunonchi: a) light multichannlpk provides guidance in obtaining the landmark in the phase of animators. It stops with the sun, forming a certain angle in relation to the location of the feed. Birds, on the other hand, will receive a target looking at The Sun when flying to remote places;

b) animals that live under sea and ocean waters, some beetles that live on land have the property of emitting light from their body. This phenomenon is called bioluminescence. Such a feature is inherent in everything from simple animals to fish.

C) light also affects the development of organisms.

Uzak for a long time iroglik influenced ettirilganda insectivorous and UVT emizuvchi ginii gulatga etis tallashgan; suv tagida yashaidigan kara-katitsa in the soul of hnmoya kilish as sovni yoritib yuboradiq sikaradi. Some of the insectivores, following Zharaenin longtatadi, Kun uzaishi bilan Isa, are companions of Keita tikladi. For this reason, the pituitary gland of beziga can have an impact, since there is no secret section, and Gini bezlarga also signals. Shundai kilib, a beast, both eruglikka and the mountain village of bir iecha, a group of such as, erogsevar, tenezevar and eraglikning uzgarishiga kengar or tor (history). In this article we will tell you how to do it yourself.

Temperature. One of the factors that determines the distribution, reproduction and other life processes of organisms in the globe is temperature. At the equator, the temperature does not change so sharply throughout the year and for one day. But as it goes from the equator to the north or south, the temperature changes by 0.5—0.6° every 100 km in flat areas. Such changes occur even in the mountainous part of the Earth shariping, when every 100 m rises to balapdlk. This means that neither all plant nor animal life processes pass in connection with these different changes. Especially in the prevalence of tumors, such changes play a special role. For this reason, the land of shariping occurs in the flat part of the plants and when the cover they form is studied into several climatic zones, chunonchi: North Pole, tundra, forest, steppe, desert, subtropical nor tropical. Plants neither live under the influence of low or high temperatures nor are they studied in two large ecological groups according to their adaptation to it.

Temperatures typically fluctuate somewhat rapidly in the terrestrial qnsmi of land shariping. In the aquatic environment, however, such changes change very slowly, especially during one day.. Most aquatic animals live normally and feed on algae even when the temperature of the water at the North Pole is 0°C. The life of the reindeer, polar bear, tyulen nor Penguins is also normal at low temperatures. Thus, for the life of gardeners, an important role is played by the total amount of the average temperature in the warmest and most cold temperatures of the ynl, the average annual temperature. The sum (quantity) of such annual temperatures is round at different points of the globe. Temperature also plays an important role in animal life. Most animals have their own constant body temperature.

In addition, moisture is also considered important. In the distribution of all organnzms on the surface of the earth, along with the temperature, the moisture factor is also important. We are not mistaken when we say that there is no life without water. In nature, water is present in various xnl forms, such manifestations as chunanchi, rain, snow, fog, pheasant, Dew, Ice, all of which represent the concept of moisture. Even so, we believe that it is preferable to use the expression water instead of the word moisture. Water accounts for 50-98% of the substances in the plant's

body. All biochemical reactions that go in cells are in the presence of water. Water is considered important for aquatic organisms.

In addition, Air is also important in preserving the ecological state. Air is considered a mixture of gases in the atmosphere, and its composition also changes depending on the change in altitude. Air is important for organisms not only as a habitat, but also as an environmental factor. In addition to gaseous natural particles, natural impurities are also found in the lower layers of the air. They can be dust and fumes, soot, sometimes crystals of sea salts, various organic particles, etc. The oxygen contained in the air is an element necessary for the respiration of plants and animals. Its amount will be enough in the air. Almost everywhere in the cities and villages of Uzbekistan, the level of air pollution does not meet sanitary requirements.

Soil. In the so-called soil, the porous, fertile surface floor of the Earth is understood. The soil is a naturally transformed outer layer of mountaineers as a result of the combined action of water, air and various organisms. The main characteristics of the soil as an environment for the organism include its natural and chemical composition, as well as the circulation of substances in it, that is, the circulation of gases, water, organic and mineral substances in an ionic state. At the same time, plant and animal species living in the soil also cause changes in its natural-chemical properties.

If we also talk a little about the current state of the soil, it will be necessary to highlight the same ones. At different points of the landmass, it should be said openly that the ecological situation in the territories of all the member republics of the Commonwealth is not very good. Especially in the lands where the peasant was engaged, the condition of the soil is poor. For example, about 70 different chemicals were used in the agricultural sector of our republic.. As a result, a large number of useful animals in the soil are destroyed, which greatly undermines human health. In the event of such a situation, the protection of nature again, including the soil, will be among the urgent problems.

Thus, it should be concluded that it is the sacred duty of all human beings today to protect all natural areas. We believe that the application of innovative approach methods in environmental education by preserving and honoring nature to students should become a necessary need.

REFERENCES

1. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 27, 2019 VM-434 "on approval of the concept of development of environmental education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, improvement of environmental education in the system of general secondary education". National database of legislative information (www.lex.uz).
2. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Work on the project "green space" in Uzbekistan. - T.: 2022 year
3. Resolution No. 3956 of October 3, 2018" on additional measures to improve the system of Public Administration in the field of Ecology and Environmental Protection".
4. Bahadirav F.N. Human anatomy. NMIU "Uzbekistan". 2006 year. Page 16.
5. Ibn Sina. Tib laws. Tashkent.: People's heritage publishing house named after Abdullah Kadiri. 1993 year.
6. Khudaykulov X.J. Qualities of perfection. - T.: Innovation-Zia.2022 y.
7. Kholmominova O.J. Ecologtk-legal education. - T.: 2021 y.
8. Khujanazarov O'. E. Yakubzhonova Sh. Ecology and nature protection. Tashkent.: Publishing house "harmonious Fayz media". 2018.148-page.